

Fidelity, Privacy, Fairness: Evaluating Synthetic Data Generators for Class-Imbalanced Clinical Data

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Abstract—Synthetic data generation is increasingly explored in healthcare as a means to address class imbalance and support privacy-preserving data sharing. However, most evaluations of synthetic tabular data focus primarily on statistical fidelity or downstream utility, without jointly considering privacy preservation and fairness, particularly in the context of minority-class augmentation. In this work, four tabular data generators (Gaussian Copula Synthesizer, Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network, Tabular Variational Autoencoder, and a Bayesian Gaussian Mixture Model with Optimal Cluster Estimation) are compared using a colorectal cancer screening dataset in which clinically important diagnostic classes are severely under-represented. We propose a three-axis evaluation framework that jointly assesses statistical fidelity, privacy preservation, and

fairness with respect to sex in synthetic records generated to balance minority classes. The evaluation is orchestrated through a multi-agent pipeline built on LangGraph, where domain-specific agents execute statistical, privacy, and fairness assessment tools, and a supervisor agent synthesizes cross-domain trade-offs into actionable recommendations. Results indicate that no single generator dominates across all three axes, revealing trades-off between distributional fidelity, privacy protection, and fairness that are particularly relevant for the smallest diagnostic classes. This study highlights the need for multi-dimensional evaluation of synthetic data in clinical settings and provides practical guidance for responsible generator selection in minority-class augmentation tasks.

Index Terms—synthetic data, data quality, privacy, fairness, agentic AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Clinical screening datasets frequently exhibit severe class imbalance, with clinically important diagnostic categories under-represented relative to healthy or low-risk groups [1]. In colorectal cancer (CRC) screening, for example, confirmed

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CRC and Advanced Adenoma (AA) cases may constitute only a small fraction of enrolled participants, while the majority of records correspond to healthy individuals or non-advanced adenomas (NAA) findings [2]. This imbalance is not unique to CRC, it arises across different rare diseases. In machine learning settings, such imbalance can limit the ability of models to learn robust decision boundaries for minority classes, where accurate classification often carries the greatest clinical consequence [3]. Therefore, augmentation strategies are needed to increase minority-class representation while maintaining realistic feature distributions and clinically meaningful inter-variable relationships [4].

Synthetic data generation has emerged as a promising approach for addressing both data scarcity and privacy constraints in healthcare [5]. By learning the statistical structure of real records and generating artificial observations, synthetic data can support model training, data sharing, and minority-class augmentation. Several families of generators have been applied to tabular clinical data, including copula-based models, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Bayesian mixture models, each offering different trade-offs in modelling capacity, training stability, and output characteristics [6], [7]. However, synthetic data are not automatically useful or safe. Specifically, a generator that produces realistic-looking samples may still distort clinically important relationships, leak information about real patients, or amplify group-level biases. For this reason, synthetic data must be evaluated across multiple dimensions, including fidelity, privacy preservation, and fairness, before it can be considered suitable for clinical use [8].

Recent work has begun to address multi-dimensional evaluation of synthetic tabular data, though most studies consider only a subset of the dimensions. Hernandez et al. [9] proposed a comprehensive framework combining fidelity, utility, and privacy metrics for synthetic data, but they did not assess downstream fairness. Bhanot et al. [10] specifically investigated the fairness implications of synthetic data in healthcare, demonstrating that generative models can introduce or amplify demographic biases, but they did not incorporate privacy assessment into their evaluation. Liu et al. [11] examined the intersection of synthetic data, fairness and privacy, proposing composite privacy and fairness scores that inform the evaluation framework adopted in this study, but they did not evaluate the statistical properties of the synthetic data. While each of these contributions advances the field, none jointly evaluates fidelity, privacy, and fairness specifically in the context of minority-class augmentation for clinical screening data.

This study addresses this gap and proposes a three-axis evaluation framework that jointly assesses statistical fidelity, privacy preservation, and fairness of synthetic tabular data generated for minority-class augmentation. The framework is applied to four representative generators: Gaussian Copula Synthesizer (GCS), Conditional Tabular GAN (CTGAN), Tabular Variational Autoencoder (TVAE), and a Bayesian Gaussian Mixture Model with Optimal Cluster Estimation (BGM-MOCE), on a real-world CRC screening dataset. Additionally,

the multi-step evaluation is orchestrated through a multi-agent pipeline built on LangGraph, where three specialist agents autonomously execute domain-specific evaluation tools via a ReAct reasoning loop, and an orchestrator agent synthesizes cross-domain trade-offs into actionable recommendations. Beyond automating metric computation, the pipeline contextualises results against established thresholds and translates numerical outputs into natural-language guidance for non-technical stakeholders.

The technical and clinical relevance of this work focus on the minority-class augmentation for AI in healthcare. Technically, the study evaluates whether different synthetic tabular data generators can balance diagnostic classes while preserving fidelity, privacy, and fairness. Clinically, this is relevant because under-represented diagnostic groups often correspond to high-risk individuals who are central to screening, prevention, and early detection. If synthetic data can improve the representation of these groups without compromising patient privacy or introducing additional bias, it may support the development of more robust and equitable clinical decision-support models.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

This work uses a clinical tabular dataset from the DIOPTRA prospective screening study (IS-RCTN15583857), which enrolled participants across nine European clinical sites. After preprocessing, the dataset comprises 1,072 participants described by 64 features and one four-class target variable (*dioptra_group_diagnosis*): Healthy (class 1, $n=459$), NAA (class 2, $n=289$), AA (class 3, $n=253$), and CRC (class 4, $n=71$). Features span four types: 4 continuous, 29 binary, 7 nominal and 24 ordinal, covering demographic, lifestyle, dietary, and clinical domains. The data were split into training (80%, $n = 857$) and test (20%, $n=215$) sets using stratified random sampling to preserve class proportions. In the training set, class frequencies are: Healthy 367, NAA 231, AA 202, and CRC 57. Synthetic data generation targets the three minority classes (NAA, AA, CRC), augmenting each to match the majority class size of 367 records. The held-out test set contains only real records and is used exclusively to evaluate fairness. More specifically, Fig. 1 illustrates the class distribution in the training set before and after synthetic augmentation.

Fig. 1: Training-set class distribution: (a) real imbalanced, (b) CTGAN-balanced.

B. Generators

Four generators from distinct generative paradigms are compared: GCS, a statistical model that captures inter-variable dependencies through a Gaussian copula [12]; CTGAN, a GAN-based model with mode-specific normalisation for mixed-type tabular data [13]; TVAE, which learns a probabilistic latent representation for tabular synthesis [14]; and BGMMOCE, a mixture-based approach that models joint distributions using Gaussian mixture models with automatically estimated components [7]. GCS, CTGAN, and TVAE are implemented via the Synthetic Data Vault (SDV) library [15].

Synthetic data were generated to match the overall training set size. This work applies each generator per minority class independently, producing enough synthetic records to bring each underrepresented class (NAA, AA, CRC) up to the majority class size of 367. This per-class strategy ensures that the balanced training sets reflect class-specific distributional characteristics rather than a single global model. CTGAN was trained for 300 epochs and TVAE for 750 epochs. All other hyperparameters were kept at default values. A unified mtadata schema specifying variable types and constraints was applied across all SDV-based generators.

For BGMMOCE, the generation pipeline proceeds in three stages per class: (1) unsupervised clustering of the class-specific training data using Self-Organising Maps (MiniSom) to discover sub-population structure, (2) selection of the optimal number of clusters by evaluating Davies-Bouldin scores and (3) fitting a Bayesian Gaussian Mixture Model with the optimal component count, diagonal covariance, and a weight concentration prior of e^{-k} , where k denotes the number of mixture components. Synthetic samples are drawn from the fitted mixture and post-processed by snapping categorical features to valid values, rounding integer columns, and clipping all features to the observed range [7].

C. Evaluation Framework (Fidelity, Privacy, Fairness)

The evaluation framework assesses synthetic data quality along three complementary axes. Since synthetic records are generated only for the three minority classes (NAA, AA, CRC), all fidelity and privacy metrics are computed by comparing the synthetic records of each class against the corresponding real training records of the same class.

Statistical fidelity quantifies how closely the synthetic feature distributions match the real training data. Five metrics are used in this evaluation. The Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence and the Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSD) measure distributional distance between real and synthetic marginal distributions [16]. The Total Variation Distance (TVD) captures differences between discrete probability distributions. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) statistic is applied to continuous features to assess whether real and synthetic samples follow similar distributions. The Cramér’s V (CV) is used to evaluate the preservation of associations between categorical features [17]. For each generator, all metrics are computed per feature within each minority class, and are then averaged first across features and then across the three minority classes to produce a

single grand-average fidelity score per generator. Lower values indicate higher fidelity across all five metrics.

Privacy preservation evaluates the risk that synthetic records could be used to reidentify real individuals or infer whether specific individuals were included in the original training data. Four metrics are employed. The Wasserstein Distance (WD) and the Jensen Shannon Divergence (JSD) between real and synthetic feature distributions are used as distributional privacy proxies. Very low values suggest that synthetic records closely resemble real records, which may increase reidentification risk [11]. K-anonymity is computed over quasi identifier columns, including *enrollment_age* binned into three groups, *sex*, and *residence_type*. This metric measures the minimum equivalence class size in the synthetic data, with higher values indicating stronger protection. The Membership Inference Attack accuracy is estimated by training a Random Forest classifier with 100 trees and five fold cross validation to distinguish real from synthetic records. Accuracy close to 0.50 indicates that the classifier cannot reliably distinguish real from synthetic samples, which suggests stronger privacy, whereas values above 0.70 indicate elevated privacy risk. A composite privacy score is computed as:

$$\text{Privacy} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\text{WD}}{\text{WD}_{\max}} + \frac{\text{JSD}}{\text{JSD}_{\max}} + \frac{\text{K}}{\text{K}_{\max}} + 1 - \frac{\text{MIA}}{\text{MIA}_{\max}} \right), \quad (1)$$

by normalising each metric to its maximum value across generators and averaging the results. The Membership Inference Attack accuracy is inverted so that higher composite scores reflect stronger privacy preservation [11]. The four privacy components are weighted equally, as no established consensus exists on the relative importance of each metric for clinical tabular data. Accordingly, all individual metrics are reported alongside the composite score to support context-specific interpretation.

Fairness evaluates whether synthetic augmentation introduces or amplifies demographic bias in downstream classification. A Random Forest classifier is trained on each balanced training set, which combines the original real records with the synthetic minority-class records, and is evaluated on the held-out real test set, which contains only real records. Three group fairness metrics are computed using *sex*, defined as female and male, as the protected attribute. The Absolute Between Receiver Operating Characteristic curve Area (ABROCA) measures the area between subgroup specific ROC curves and captures differences in classification behaviour between groups. The Error Rate Difference (ERD) measures the absolute difference in false positive rates between groups. The True Positive Rate Difference (TPRD) measures the absolute difference in true positive rates between groups [11]. All three metrics are averaged across diagnostic classes. A real only baseline trained without synthetic augmentation is used as the reference point. A composite fairness score is computed as:

$$\text{Fairness} = \frac{1}{3} (3 - |\text{ABROCA}| - |\text{ERD}| - |\text{TPRD}|), \quad (2)$$

where values closer to 1.0 indicate higher parity [11]. Equal weights are assigned to the three fairness components in the

absence of a clinically validated weighting scheme for this screening context. For this reason, each individual metric is also reported separately, allowing readers to prioritise the dimensions most relevant to their specific clinical application.

D. Agentic AI

Evaluating synthetic data across three axes with multiple metrics per axis and four generators produces a complex decision space where manual interpretation is both time-consuming and prone to oversight. To address this, the evaluation pipeline is orchestrated through a multi-agent system built on LangGraph [18]. The architecture consists of four agents arranged in a fan-out/fan-in topology. Three specialist agents, responsible for statistical fidelity, privacy, and fairness respectively, execute in parallel. A fourth orchestrator agent synthesises their outputs once all three have completed.

Each specialist agent is backed by a local large language model (Qwen3:8b, served via Ollama) and is equipped with domain-specific evaluation tools exposed as callable functions. Agents operate through a ReAct reasoning loop in which the LLM observes tool outputs, reasons about intermediate results, and autonomously decides which tool to invoke next. For example, the privacy agent first computes distributional distances for all generators. If a generator exhibits unusually low Wasserstein distance, the agent selectively triggers the more computationally expensive membership inference attack simulation. This conditional, result-dependent tool invocation distinguishes the pipeline from a fixed scripted workflow.

Fig. 2: Implementation architecture of the agentic system.

The supervisor agent receives validated structured results and natural-language summaries from all three specialists. Without access to evaluation tools itself, it performs cross-domain reasoning, identifying trade-offs between axes (e.g. a generator with strong fidelity but weak privacy), ranking generators, and producing actionable recommendations. All inference runs locally, ensuring that no patient-derived data or evaluation outputs leave the institutional environment.

III. RESULTS

Results are presented along the three evaluation axes. For each axis, a summary table reports the per-generator metrics, followed by a brief interpretation highlighting the best and worst performers and the magnitude of observed differences.

A. Statistical Fidelity

Table I reports the SDV diagnostic scores for each generator. CTGAN achieves the highest overall score (90.05%), with the strongest performance in both column shapes (92.78%) and column pair trends (87.31%), indicating superior preservation of marginal distributions and bivariate relationships. TVAE scores lowest overall (81.79%), primarily due to weaker column pair trends (75.98%).

TABLE I: SDV Quality Report

Model	Column Shapes	Column Pair Trends	Score
GCS	90.59%	86.19%	88.39%
CTGAN	92.78%	87.31%	90.05%
TVAE	87.61%	75.98%	81.79%
BGMMOCE	87.98%	77.06%	82.52%

Table II reports grand-average fidelity metrics across all minority classes and features. For all metrics, lower values indicate a closer statistical similarity between synthetic and real data. CTGAN achieves the best distributional fidelity across most metrics, with the lowest KL divergence (0.0890), JSD (0.0208), TVD (0.1018), and Cramér’s V (0.0935). However, its KS statistic (0.3138) is the highest among all generators, suggesting that while CTGAN captures categorical structure well, its continuous feature distributions deviate more noticeably from the real data. GCS achieves the lowest KS statistic (0.1511), indicating the closest match on continuous features. TVAE shows the weakest overall fidelity, with KL divergence (0.7223) roughly eight times higher than CTGAN and the highest JSD and TVD values. BGMMOCE performs at an intermediate level, with fidelity metrics comparable to GCS but higher KL divergence.

TABLE II: Statistical Similarity Metrics

Model	KL	JSD	TVD	KS	CV
GCS	0.3247	0.0387	0.1236	0.1511	0.1329
CTGAN	0.0890	0.0208	0.1018	0.3138	0.0935
TVAE	0.7223	0.0476	0.1474	0.2209	0.1913
BGMMOCE	0.4001	0.0465	0.1426	0.2060	0.1675

B. Privacy Preservation

Table III shows that CTGAN achieves the highest composite privacy score (0.6271), driven by both the largest Wasserstein distance (0.6438) and the only K-Anonymity value above 1 ($k=11$), indicating that its synthetic records form larger equivalence classes over the quasi-identifier set. CTGAN also exhibits the lowest JSD (0.0208), suggesting that while its synthetic records differ from real records in magnitude, the overall shape of feature distributions remains similar. TVAE ranks second (0.5123), with moderate distributional distance but K-Anonymity of 1. GCS and BGMMOCE score lowest (0.4076 and 0.4398 respectively), both exhibiting K-Anonymity of 1 and the smallest Wasserstein distances, meaning that their synthetic records remain close to real values and that at least one synthetic record is uniquely identifiable by the quasi-identifier combination of age group, sex, and residence type.

A critical finding is that MIA accuracy is consistently high across all generators, ranging from 0.8702 (TVAE) to 0.9319 (BGMMOCE). These values substantially exceed the 0.50 ideal, indicating that a Random Forest classifier can reliably distinguish real from synthetic records regardless of the generation method. BGMMOCE exhibits the highest MIA accuracy, followed by GCS (0.8993) and CTGAN (0.8975). The composite privacy score does not fully reflect this vulnerability due to relative normalisation across generators.

TABLE III: Privacy Preservation Metrics

Model	WD	JSD	K-Anonymity	MIA Accuracy	Privacy Score
GCS	0.4230	0.0387	1	0.8993	0.4076
CTGAN	0.6438	0.0208	11	0.8975	0.6271
TVAE	0.5529	0.0476	1	0.8702	0.5123
BGMMOCE	0.4452	0.0465	1	0.9319	0.4398

C. Fairness

Table IV reports fairness metrics for a Random Forest trained on each balanced dataset and evaluated on the real test set. A real-only baseline is included for comparison. Lower ABROCA, ERD, and TPRD indicate greater parity across sex subgroups. TVAE achieves the lowest ABROCA (0.0765) and ERD (0.0060) among all generators, indicating the smallest divergence in ROC curves and false positive rates between sex subgroups. However, it also exhibits the highest TPRD (0.0479), which means that while TVAE equalizes error rates between groups, it introduces a gap in true positive rates. This suggests that fairness is not a single-dimensional property, and that generators may improve parity on one fairness metric while worsening another. BGMMOCE shows the opposite pattern, with the lowest ERD (0.0058) but the highest ABROCA (0.1318), further illustrating that individual fairness metrics can diverge even when composite scores remain similar.

The narrow spread of fairness scores (less than 0.01 between best and worst) suggests that the choice of generator has a limited effect on downstream fairness in this dataset. The real-only baseline is nearly identical to the best generator (TVAE), providing reassurance that minority-class augmentation can be applied without introducing additional demographic bias.

TABLE IV: Fairness Preservation Metrics

Model	ABROCA	ERD	TPRD	Fairness Score
Real-only	0.0984	0.0106	0.0217	0.9564
GCS	0.1293	0.0167	0.0081	0.9487
CTGAN	0.1100	0.0139	0.0189	0.9524
TVAE	0.0765	0.0060	0.0479	0.9565
BGMMOCE	0.1318	0.0058	0.0407	0.9406

D. Agentic Evaluation

The supervisor agent synthesized the findings from the three specialist agents into an integrated assessment. Based on the combined evidence across all three evaluation axes, CTGAN was identified as the strongest overall generator, achieving the best statistical fidelity and the highest composite privacy score (0.6271), with competitive fairness (0.9524). TVAE was ranked second overall, with the best fairness score (0.9565)

but the weakest distributional fidelity. GCS and BGMMOCE were ranked third and fourth respectively, with moderate performance across all axes.

The supervisor identified two cross-domain findings that are not apparent from any single evaluation axis. First, CTGAN achieves both the strongest fidelity and the highest privacy score, suggesting that adversarial training can produce synthetic records that are distributionally faithful without necessarily increasing re-identification risk. Second, TVAE exhibits the weakest fidelity but the highest fairness, indicating that a lower distributional accuracy does not necessarily amplify demographic bias and may in some cases reduce it.

The supervisor also flagged one concern shared across all generators. MIA accuracy consistently exceeds 0.85, indicating that a classifier can reliably distinguish real from synthetic records regardless of the generation method. Beyond this, the agent identified generator-specific weaknesses: TVAE and BGMMOCE were flagged for KL divergence above the 0.30 threshold, suggesting inadequate distributional alignment with the real data. For these generators, the agent recommended hyperparameter optimisation and exploration of hybrid approaches combining variational or mixture-based methods with adversarial training to improve fidelity. As an overarching recommendation, the agent prioritised the integration of differential privacy mechanisms and fidelity-aware training strategies to jointly address the privacy vulnerability and statistical validity concerns identified across all generators.

E. Generators Comparison

Table V provides a consolidated view of generator performance across all three evaluation axes. CTGAN emerges as the strongest overall candidate, achieving the best performance in both statistical fidelity and privacy preservation. Notably, TVAE ranks last in fidelity but first in fairness, while CTGAN ranks first in fidelity but second in fairness. This inverse pattern further supports the fidelity-fairness trade-off suggesting that higher distributional accuracy may come at the cost of equitable classifier behaviour across demographic subgroups.

TABLE V: Overall Appearance of Each Generator

Evaluation Axis	Best Performer	Worst Performer
Statistical Fidelity	CTGAN	TVAE
Privacy Preservation	CTGAN	GCS
Fairness	TVAE	BGMMOCE

IV. DISCUSSION

The comparison across fidelity, privacy, and fairness reveals that generator strengths on one axis do not predict performance on the others. CTGAN achieves the best distributional fidelity and the highest composite privacy score, yet ranks only second in fairness. TVAE, which produces the least accurate distributional copies, yields the most equitable downstream classifiers. One plausible explanation is that generators with lower distributional precision introduce noise that attenuates subgroup-specific patterns present in the real data, leading to classifiers that behave more uniformly across demographic

groups. Higher fidelity generators, by contrast, may replicate existing disparities more faithfully. This fidelity-fairness trade-off carries direct implications for clinical screening, where decision-makers must weigh whether preserving every statistical nuance of the training data is preferable to producing classifiers that treat patient subgroups more equitably.

Across all four generators, MIA accuracy remains high (0.8702 to 0.9319), meaning that a standard classifier can identify whether a record was part of the real training set with near-certainty. The composite privacy score obscures this vulnerability because relative normalisation compresses the signal when every generator fails on the same dimension. This is especially problematic for the CRC class ($n=57$), where the small pool of real records means each individual's data exerts substantial influence on the learned generative model. Addressing this limitation will likely require incorporating explicit privacy guarantees such as differential privacy directly into the training objective of the generators.

The agentic evaluation pipeline extends beyond a fixed scripted workflow by reasoning conditionally over intermediate results and selectively invoking computationally expensive tools, such as MIA simulation, when distributional proxies indicate elevated risk. The orchestrator agent further adds value by translating raw metric outputs into contextualised assessments and mitigation-oriented recommendations. For example, it can identify that fidelity and fairness trade-offs may lead to different generator choices depending on whether the intended use prioritises screening sensitivity, demographic equity, or privacy preservation. While the current pipeline does not autonomously implement its recommendations, it supports clinically safer decisions about whether synthetic data should be trusted, restricted, or rejected before downstream model development. This distinguishes the framework from prior evaluations by combining fidelity, privacy, and fairness assessment with an agentic recommendation layer before mitigation is applied.

Technically, the contribution is a unified evaluation protocol that combines fidelity, re-identification risk, and fairness assessment for minority-class augmentation, coupled with an agentic pipeline for cross-axis trade-off detection. Clinically, the findings extend to any screening programme in which the most important diagnostic categories are the rarest. The fidelity-fairness trade-off documented here offers actionable guidance for clinical teams selecting a generation strategy, and the privacy findings signal that generators alone are insufficient to guarantee confidentiality for small patient cohorts.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented a three-axis evaluation framework for assessing synthetic tabular data generators used in minority-class augmentation, jointly measuring fidelity, privacy preservation, and fairness on a colorectal cancer screening dataset. The comparison of four generators (GCS, CTGAN, TVAE, BGMMOCE) revealed that no single method dominates across all axes: CTGAN achieved the strongest fidelity and privacy, while TVAE produced the fairest classifiers at the cost of

distributional accuracy. A persistent privacy vulnerability was identified across all generators, with MIA accuracy exceeding 0.87, highlighting the need for integrating differential privacy mechanisms into the generation process. The LangGraph-based agentic pipeline automated cross-domain evaluation and surfaced trade-offs for informed generator selection. Future work will extend the framework to additional clinical datasets, incorporate privacy-aware generation methods, and evaluate fairness across multiple protected attributes.

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